

SOCIAL DISCRIMINATION AMONG THE NURSES IN A TERTIARY HOSPITAL DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC: AN ASSESSMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13912886>

ABSTRACT

This quantitative research study aims to assess how nurses from tertiary hospitals experienced social discrimination during the COVID-19 pandemic. With this in mind, the researcher collected data among the one hundred (100) nurses from different departments at a tertiary hospital in Cavite City. The data acquired were the profiles of the chosen respondents and the experiences of the nurses with social discrimination in terms of felt stigma, direct stigma, and indirect stigma. The researcher will determine if there are significant relationships between the profile and the assessments of the shared experiences. The study also underscores determining the challenges that hinder the nurses from performing their responsibilities during COVID-19; thus, it will help the study propose an action plan to be provided in times of emergency. A survey questionnaire will be distributed to the carefully selected nurse respondents in order to collect necessary data. The tool will be crafted by the researcher, who will seek validation from three experts. Based on the results, in terms of felt stigma, most nurses encountered rants with a mean of 3.02, interpreted as somewhat extensive. In the indicator of direct stigma, the majority encountered being talked about, with a mean of 4.91, or to a large extent. Finally, indirect stigma occurs when people spread incorrect information about the nurse respondents, which comprise 3.02 or are interpreted as to some extent. Some recommendations are trainings or workshops highlighting psychosocial support, psychospiritual well-being, and mental health awareness programs for healthcare workers. The other suggested recommendations were enumerated in the action plan provided.

Keywords: *Social discrimination, felt stigma, direct stigma, indirect stigma*

INTRODUCTION

The advent of the COVID-19 pandemic impacts numerous fields, including business, education, travel and tourism, and, most importantly, people's health and well-being. No one is exempt to the fact that the worldwide epidemic created a great deal of stress and health problems, both physically and emotionally. The healthcare staff that are in charge of ensuring the well-being of the patients are on the front lines of these problems. Many healthcare personnel encountered social discrimination throughout the pandemic's rise.

Labrague (2021) claims that social discrimination occurs when a person repeatedly encounters unfairness as a result of their sickness, handicap, religion, sexual orientation, or other distinctive characteristics. They were treated differently because of how they distinguished out from other people. The worst-case situation is when they do not receive the same advantages or provisions due to bias or judgment. Beyond the physical health of those who are afflicted, COVID-19's impacts also manifest as emotional and psychological problems brought on by social exclusion, stigma, and social prejudice. Many people face a social conundrum related to the practice of isolating patients who tested positive, and those who have strong relationships with these people also faced prejudice. The people most impacted by this problem are the group of healthcare professionals. When people encounter nurses, doctors, or other hospital staff, many avoid them. For the sake of their families' protection, health workers are occasionally compelled to stay away from home. To make sure they are not infected with a virus, they must give up at least two weeks of isolation.

Healthcare professionals, according to (Koontalay, et al., 2021)., are the most stressed out COVID-19 combatants because, in addition to providing their services, they also have to battle discrimination. According to the same post, an ambulance driver was shot on April 3, 2020, for parking his vehicle in a residential neighborhood after transferring medical people. According to reports, the suspect was worried that the driver would infect the entire town. In Sultan Kudarat province, a teenage utility worker at a hospital was ganged up on by five guys and drenched with bleach. He sustained eye injuries and faces irreversible blindness. A supermarket security guard lost both her rented apartment and her job when a thermal scan revealed that her temperature was higher than 36 degrees Celsius (Ornedo, 2020). Lastly, a motorcycle-riding tandem splattered chlorine on a nurse who was on his way home from duty in Cebu City in the Visayas. These are just some of the social discriminations reported incidence experienced by health workers during COVID-19.

To resist the virus's enormous burden, emotional and psychological stability is essential. Health staff, like everyone else, is also terrified. Their immunity is also weakened as a result of their intimate interaction with the patients. In reality, one out of every ten deaths taken by COVID-19 in the country is that of a doctor or a healthcare worker. In an interview with GMA News, a nurse said, "Do not think us dirty and shun us". These professionals

still have the right to go about their regular lives, eating, doing laundry, shopping for groceries, and travelling without worrying about what others think of them. To relieve this societal stigma, the government takes action by informing those who intend to discriminate against healthcare authorities and staff. In Cebu City, an ordinance was passed that imposes penalties and a six-month prison sentence on anyone who discriminates against and denies healthcare workers access to services. They raise awareness about how people should respect healthcare staff while they combat the global epidemic. The mayors of Metro Manila issued a resolution encouraging local governments to sanction people who discriminate against frontliners, distressed Filipino migrants from COVID-19 impacted nations, and patients. On the other hand, the general people must be kind and take preventative precautions without intruding on the rights of others.

The researcher, who is one of the experts who battled for the country's safety and welfare, chose to undertake a study that would contribute to the field. During COVID-19, a tertiary hospital in General Trias City, Cavite, Philippines, also provided medical assistance. A tertiary level hospital is one that can provide medical care to situations that require advanced diagnostic and therapeutic technology as well as the skills of trained experts and sub-specialists. It provides a broad range of services including pediatrics, obstetrics, general medicine, gynecology, several types of surgery, and psychiatric or a hospital specialized to specialized sub-specialty treatment (pediatric centers, oncology centers, psychiatric hospitals). The tertiary hospital mentioned in this study consists of different departments namely Emergency Unit, COVID-Wing Unit, Intensive Care Unit, New-born Intensive Care Unit, Operating Room, Delivery Room, Hemodialysis, and General Nursing Unit.

In The aforementioned circumstances, the researcher was prompted to conduct a study that will solely contribute to the field she is engaged. Specifically, this paper aimed to determine the social discrimination among the one-hundred (100) nurses in a tertiary hospital during COVID-19 pandemic. At the end of this research, it will greatly help on providing recommendation among healthcare professionals how to alleviate the problems on the experienced social discrimination that may occur in the future.

Research Questions

The researcher primarily aimed to assess how nurses from tertiary hospital encountered social discrimination during COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, sought answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. position; and
 - 1.4. number of years in profession?
2. How is social discrimination among the nurses can be assessed in terms of:
 - 2.1. felt stigma;
 - 2.2. direct stigma; and

- 2.3. indirect stigma?
3. Is there any significant relationship between their demographic profile and the social discrimination experienced by the nurses?
 4. What action plan can be developed for the encountered social discrimination among the nurses?

Hypotheses

There is no significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the social discrimination encountered during COVID-19.

The encountered social discrimination among the nurses during COVID-19 is high.

METHODOLOGY

Research Method Used

Quantitative research approach was used in this study. According to Lani (2018), quantitative research uses deductive logic, in which the researcher starts with hypothesis and then collects data which can be used to determine whether empirical evidence to support that hypothesis exists.

This approach was used because the researcher wanted to assess the social discrimination among the nurses during COVID-19. Two designs were utilized in this research, first, descriptive research design for research question number 2. Williams (2007) said that it is suitable for examining a current state, or situation.

Another design is the correlational research design. According to Kalla (2019), correlational study seeks to determine whether the variables are related or not. In simple terms, the researcher tried to understand what kind of relationship is involved in the variables with one another. This design was employed because the researcher looked into significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the assessments in social discrimination.

Population Frame and Sampling Scheme

The researcher concentrated among the one hundred (100) nurses from a tertiary hospital. These respondents were purposively selected by the researcher. Purposive sampling is choosing the subset from a larger population. This sampling technique was used since the researcher looked for respondents who qualified for the purpose of getting responses from nurses in a tertiary hospital. Total population of the nurses from the emergency department, intensive care unit; newborn intensive care unit; operating room; three hemodialysis; COVID wing; and in general nursing participated in the administration of the survey questionnaire.

Below is the specification of the respondents:

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

TERTIARY HOSPITAL			
Department	Number of Nurses	Number who Participated	Percentage
Emergency Department	16	16	16
Delivery Room	7	7	7
Intensive Care Unit	10	10	10
Newborn intensive care unit	11	11	11
Operating Room	9	9	9
Hermodialysis	9	9	9
4th GNU right wing clean case	9	9	9
4TH GNU left wing transition case	9	9	9
4TH GNU left wing transition case	10	10	10
4TH GNU left wing transition case	10	10	10
Total	100	100	100%

Description of the Respondents

The Genti Medical and Hospital Inc. is a tertiary hospital located in General Trias City, Cavite Philippines. It is located on a 3,500 square meter property which is easily accessible. It has 7,000 square meters of floor area and a seven-story structure that can accommodate up to 100 beds. It is made up of over 40 medical professionals as founding members and renowned medical staff of over 100 physicians; all of them are seasoned and acknowledged specialists in their respective fields of specialty and administration.

Two nursing departments were being supervised by the researcher in this study, the emergency department and COVID Wing Department.

Research Instrument

The researcher used a survey questionnaire among the respondents to gather the necessary data for the study at hand. According to McLeod (2018), survey questionnaire is a research instrument consisting of a series of questions for the purpose of gathering information from respondents. The components of this survey questionnaire were based on the statement of the problem questions in Chapter 1. Part 1 focused on the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, position and number of years in the position. Part 2 focused on assessing the social discrimination encountered by nurses in a tertiary hospital during COVID-19. This includes the key factors such as felt stigma, direct stigma and indirect stigma. To test the reliability of the result gathered from the instrument, the researcher will consider Cronbach's Alpha, Internal consistency, or how closely related a group of items are to one another, is measured by Cronbach's alpha. It is regarded as a scale reliability indicator. To ensure the validity of the research

instrument, before the administration of survey questionnaire among the respondents, the researcher has undergone procedures for validation. The questionnaire was presented to the adviser for comments and suggestions. The researcher also sought from experts to validate the content, language and format of the tool. A pilot testing was conducted to test and validate the survey questionnaire among nurses not included in the study.

Reliability and Validity

The researcher requested the assistance and collaboration of other involved parties who got in touch with the respondents directly to ease the distribution of pilot survey questionnaires. After receiving permission from the hospital administration, the researcher performed the study using a survey questionnaire for the nurses at the Genti Doctors Medical Center, which is close to my neighborhood in Governor's Dr., General Trias, Cavite. The 15 nurses from the facility who participated in this pilot test were distributed it in October 2022. The reliability test results using IBM SPSS Statistics version 24 are shown below.

Table 2 Test of Reliability

Subscales	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Internal Consistency
Felt Stigma	8	0.973	Excellent
Direct Stigma	9	0.898	Excellent
Indirect Stigma	10	0.897	Excellent

With a Cronbach's alpha of more than 0.700, the questionnaire utilized by nurses in their practices demonstrated a high degree of reliability, as can be seen from the provided table. It is important to note that all subscales of social discrimination against nurses may be evaluated in terms of perceived stigma, direct stigma, and indirect stigma. This demonstrates an exceptional degree of internal consistency across the stated items. Because the items were developed consistently by the researcher, the study's questionnaire has a high degree of reproducibility.

Data Gathering Procedures

To secure indispensable gathering of data among the respondents, data collection was performed into two means. It could be through face-to-face and distance modality. This varied depending on the availability of the nurses scheduled. This helped the researcher gather simultaneously and let the respondents concentrate in answering the questionnaire.

Prior to the administration of the tool, the researcher sought approval from the department head of the tertiary hospital. This was done by sending a letter addressed to the officer-in-charge through the supervisory head of the nursing department. Once approved, the researcher then secured consent among the respondents. This was to ensure data privacy agreement between the parties. The printed survey questionnaires were distributed among the respondents and were collected. The researcher allowed a maximum of two days for contemplating their answers in the survey questionnaire.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To answer the problems identified in this research, the data were presented on tables and statistically treated for accurate analysis and interpretation. Hence, to provide a reliable interpretation of the data to be gathered, the researcher utilized the statistics such as Percentage, Weighted Mean and Chi-square Correlation.

Percentage, a frequency distribution, is a display of data that specifies the percentage of observations that exist for each data point or grouping of data points. It was used to measure the specific points to a whole in identifying the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, position, and number of years in service. One of the most frequent ways to represent statistics is by percentage. The percentage formula is defined as

$$Percentage = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

where: % = Percentage

f = frequency

N = Number of Cases

Weighted Mean to determine the average responses of respondents on various key indicators considered in the study, particularly on assessing the social discrimination encountered by the nurses. The formula for weighted mean is.

$$WD = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

where:

WM - weighted mean

f - frequency

x - the assigned weight

N - total number of respondents

$\sum fx$ - is the sum of frequency multiplied by the assigned

weight

Standard Deviation it provides an indication of how far the individual responses to a question vary or "deviate" from the mean. It was used in the data of description of assessment that measure of the spread of scores within a set of data on Social Discrimination. The formula for standard deviation is.

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x - \bar{x})^2}{n - 1}}$$

where,

s = sample standard deviation

\sum = sum of...

\bar{x} = sample mean

n = number of scores in sample.

Chi-square to compare observed results with expected results. The purpose of this test that there is no significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and the social discrimination encountered during COVID-19. The formula for chi-square is.

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Where:

χ^2 = Chi Squared

O_i = Observed Value

E_i = Expected Value

To interpret the assessments of the respondents, this will be utilized:

Assessment on Social Discrimination during COVID-19		
Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.20-5.00	To a great extent
4	3.40-4.19	To a large extent
3	2.60-3.39	Somewhat extent
2	1.80-2.39	Little extent
	1.00-1.79	Not at All

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results of the study, the statistical analysis of data, and the corresponding interpretation and discussion.

5. The profile of the respondents in terms of:

5.1 Age

Table 3 Demographic Profile of Respondents in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
41-50	6	6
31-40	51	51
21-30	43	43

Total	100	100
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It reveals that 51 percent of the population, or 51 out of 100 nurses, range their age between 31 and 40. Additionally, 43 out of 100 nurses are between the ages of 21 and 30, making up 43 percent of the overall population. On the other hand, no nurses working in Cavite City's Tertiary Hospital are between the ages of 51 and 60 or older.

This presents that majority of the respondents in a tertiary hospital is 31-40, which means most of the nurses belong to the adult category. The study of Masum et al., (2016) focused on investigating the effect of demographic variables of their nurse-respondents. Age and educational level have been reported to be significant to turnover retention, with younger and higher educated nurses being more likely to show turnover retention.

5.2. Gender

Table 4 Demographic Profile of Respondents in Terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
F	56	56
M	44	44
Total	100	100

Table 4 reveals that just 44 out of every 100 nurses are men, making about 44 percent of the overall population. 56 out of every 100 nurses are female, making up 56 percent of the workforce.

It simply implies that there are more female nurses than male nurses at the Tertiary Hospital in Cavite City, which indicates that women have superior nursing abilities. However, it is observed that there is an equal distribution of nurses in a tertiary hospital in terms of their gender. According to Prosen (2022) both male and female nursing are aware of the limitations imposed by their own gender roles, but they are ready to question these stereotypes.

5.3. Position

Position/Department	Frequency	Percent
4th Left Wing Awaiting RT PCR	14	14
4th Right Wing Clean Case	15	10
5th Covid Wing	10	10

Delivery Room	10	10
Emergency Room	16	16
Intensive Care Unit	11	11
Neonatal Intensive Care Unit	10	10
Operating Room	14	14
Total	100	100

Table 5 Demographic Profile of Respondents in Terms of Position

It demonstrates in table 5 that, out of the eight places, position 16 out of 100, or the emergency room, has the highest frequency with 16 percent. 15 out of 100 with a 15% accuracy came next, making it the fourth right wing clean case. Like the delivery room, the neonatal intensive care unit, and the fifth covid wing, each of which has 10 nurses out of 100, or 10 percent of the total population, have the same number of nurses. Finally, 11 percent of the hospital's nurses, or 11 out of 100, work in the intensive care unit. The Emergency Room appears to need the most help each time a patient enters a hospital, thus there are apparently more nurses working there. The nurses' practical role requires them to completely attend to the patient's fundamental treatment.

5.4. Number of Years in Profession

Table 6 Demographic Profile of Respondents in Terms of Number of Years in Profession

5 years and below	90	90
Total	100	100

Length of Service	Frequency	Percent
6-10	10	10

Table 6 reveals that 90 percent of the population has less than five years' experience in the nursing industry, or 90 out of 100 people. While the remaining 10 percent, or 10 people out of 100, have 6 to 10 years of nursing experience at Cavite City's Tertiary Hospital. It simply indicates that the majority of the hospital's nurses are new to the profession and are developing expertise in their area of expertise based on the study of Viscardi et al (2022).

6. Social discrimination among the nurse's assessment in terms of:

6.1 Felt Stigma

Table 7 Assessment on Social Discrimination in Terms of Felt Stigma

Felt Stigma	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. hearing rants	3.13	1.12	Somewhat Extent
2. insulting gestures	3.06	0.98	Somewhat Extent
3. blaming	3.06	1.03	Somewhat Extent
4. using foul or offensive words	2.96	.96	Somewhat Extent
5. social loathing	3.04	.94	Somewhat Extent
6. hearing curses	2.90	.78	Somewhat Extent
7. harassed through calls	2.97	.88	Somewhat Extent
8. harassed through tweets	3.01	.86	Somewhat Extent
Overall	3.02	0.94	Somewhat Extent

Legend: 4.21 – 5.00 – Great Extent; 3.41 – 4.20 – Large Extent; 2.61 – 3.40 – Somewhat Extent; 1.81 – 2.60 – Little Extent;

1.00 – 1.80 – Not at all

Table 6 displays the total mean of 3.02 and 0.94 standard deviation, which is taken as showing a degree of social prejudice experienced during the COVID-19 epidemic. The highest mean of 3.13 and 1.12 standard deviation indicates that there is some degree of hearing rants based on perceived stigma. In contrast, the lowest mean of 2.90 and 0.78 standard deviation, which is taken as a certain degree of hearing expletives. It only demonstrates the amount to which stigma-seeking conduct occurs in a limited way.

Both people experienced some degree of stigma in relation to the blaming and insulting gestures, which had a 3.06 mean and 0.98 and 1.03 standard deviations, respectively. Like the social hatred and harassment of tweets, which indicate 3.01 and 3.04 mean and 0.86 and 0.94 standard deviation, which to some degree contribute to the stigma against nurses. While using vulgar or unpleasant language and harassing through calls slightly extends that during the COVID-19 epidemic. It conceptualizes our health-related stigmas and practical experience to some part based on the perceived stigma existence by building from felt stigma which is already present.

According to the study of Maji S, Bansod S and Singh T. (2022). examines discrimination based on race, class, and religion as well as the stigma associated with the COVID-19 epidemic across various socioeconomic groups in Indian culture using secondary data gathered from news articles that have been published online or in print. Their study reveals that stigma, in addition to the emphasis on COVID-19 therapy and prevention, lowers health-, help-, and treatment-seeking behavior and needs to be reduced. In the development of illnesses, global health communication is crucial.

Direct Stigma

Table 8 Assessment on Social Discrimination in Terms of Direct Stigma

Direct Stigma	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Being talked about	4.91	0.28	Great Extent
2. Offensive jokes	3.98	0.20	Large Extent
3. "Aloof" treatment	4.18	0.41	Large Extent
4. Creating memes in social media	4.00	0.00	Large Extent
5. Physical loathing	3.01	0.85	Somewhat Extent
6. Social media bashing	3.98	0.20	Large Extent
7. Attacked physically	4.18	0.41	Large Extent
8. Harassed through group chats	3.01	0.85	Somewhat Extent
9. Barricade my house	4.42	0.91	Great Extent
Overall	3.96	0.46	Large Extent

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00 - Great Extent; 3.41 - 4.20 - Large Extent; 2.61 - 3.40 - Somewhat Extent; 1.81 - 2.60 - Little Extent; 1.00 - 1.80 - Not at all

Table 7 demonstrates that nurses were evaluated on social discriminations in terms of direct stigma to a great extent, with an overall mean of 3.96 and a standard deviation of 0.46. The greatest possible mean of 4.91 and the lowest possible standard deviation of 0.28 show that direct stigma has a much greater impact than simply being spoken about. While the lowest mean of 3.01 and 0.85 standard deviation is perceived as a slight degree of physical hatred and harassment through group chats that is a direct stigma among the nurses, it merely demonstrates how societal prejudice against particular people leads to acts of direct stigmatization.

The second-highest mean of 4.42 and 0.91 standard deviation indicates a significant degree of direct blockade of the home, which demonstrates blatant social inequality. Additionally, the median values of 4.18 and 4.0, which demonstrate a significant degree of the direct stigma of being physically assaulted and by making memes on social media, have a significant influence on social prejudice. With a mean of 3.98 and a standard deviation of 0.20, which is viewed as a substantial amount of direct stigma, social discrimination is directly stigmatized along with online trolling and inappropriate humor. Only a trait that causes direct stigmatization has a consistent impact on social exclusionary practices.

Based on the study of He, He, Zhou, Nie, and He (2020), people of Chinese or Asian heritage have consistently faced prejudice and social marginalization on a global scale. Numerous media sources from all over the world have documented instances of prejudice against people of Asian heritage taking place in public since the epidemic began in January, including on the bus, in shopping centers, on the street, and on school campuses. The types of discriminatory behavior ranged from physical assaults to verbal insults.

6.2. Indirect Stigma

Indirect Stigma	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Forced quarantine	4.30	0.46	Great Extent
2. Shunning away of people	4.63	0.49	Great Extent
3. Spreading wrong information about me	4.81	0.39	Great Extent
4. Refused rides on buses or other public transportation	4.44	0.67	Great Extent
5. Denial of access to essential services (haircut, laundry, eateries, etc.)	3.02	0.96	Somewhat Extent
6. Petitioned (ex. Transfer)	4.51	0.50	Great Extent
7. Harassment of my family and close friends	3.03	0.86	Somewhat Extent
8. Evicted from dormitories/apartment	4.51	0.50	Great Extent
9. Doused on my way to work	4.30	0.46	Great Extent
10. family and close friends are denied of essential services	4.44	0.67	Great Extent

Overall	4.21	0.60	Great Extent
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Table 9 Assessment on Social Discrimination in Terms of Indirect Stigma

Legend: 4.21 - 5.00 - Great Extent; 3.41 - 4.20 - Large Extent; 2.61 - 3.40 - Somewhat Extent; 1.81 - 2.60 - Little Extent; 1.00 - 1.80 - Not at all

Table 8 demonstrates that the overall mean of 4.21 and the 0.60 standard deviation are considered as significant amounts in the evaluation of nurses in terms of indirect stigma discovered in social discrimination. The greatest mean of 4.81 and a standard deviation of 0.39 concur that social discrimination's indirect stigmatization of others to a significant degree is reflected in this data. While the lowest mean of 3.02 and 0.96 standard deviation indicates some degree of access denial to necessary services like haircuts, laundry, restaurants, and many other things. It only demonstrates indirect discrimination when a practice or policy applies to everyone equally yet has an adverse impact on some individuals more than others.

The two averages of 4.51 and 0.50 standard deviations demonstrate a significant amount of people being petitioned or transferred, kicked out of their apartments or dorms, and subjected to social discrimination. Additionally, With a mean of 4.44 and a standard deviation of 0.67, social prejudice against relatives and close friends is prevalent. They are also frequently refused rides on buses and other forms of public transit. Additionally, the shunning of individuals has a significant impact, including indirect social discrimination through stigma. According to these findings, those who have a certain protected attribute may be at a specific disadvantage in terms of social discrimination among nurses who experience indirect stigma.

According to Logie and Turan (2020), it may be possible to lessen stigma by balancing pandemic containment and prevention measures, such as physical separation and travel restrictions, with appropriate information/public health messages and participation of communities that are negatively impacted by the pandemic (such as women, LGBTQI people, people of marginalized races, and the poor).

7. Significant relationship between their profile and the social discrimination experienced by the nurses.

Table 10 Relationship Between Social Discrimination and Demographic Profile

Assessment on Social Discrimination	Chi2	df	Asymptotic Significance (p-value 2-sided)	Decision
Age	2.02	3	0.568	Accept Ho

Gender	1.77	3	0.622	Accept Ho
Years in Service	2.86	3	0.413	Accept Ho
Position	53.57	3	<.001	Reject Ho

The relationship between social discrimination and the demographic profile of nurses is shown in Table 9, where only the position of the nurse needs to reject the null hypothesis. Based on the results of the 53.57 chi-square test, the p-value for this relationship is 0.001, indicating that there is a significant relationship between the social discrimination and the position. This only indicates that stigmas exist in certain nursing positions or departments.

According to Abuhammad (2020) they stated that there is a significant increase in racist views, bullying, discriminating behaviors, and hostile acts directed towards these people, which were later extended to those who were affected or had recovered from the sickness, their family members, and healthcare workers.

The social discrimination in terms of perceived stigma, direct stigma, and indirect stigma shows no significant relationship between the age, gender, or years of service. Age has a p-value of 0.568, gender has a p-value of 0.622, and years of service have a p-value of 0.413; these values all indicate larger than the significant threshold of 0.05, which leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. It demonstrates that age, gender, and years of service have no significant relationship between the demographic profile with stigmas, demonstrating that each nurse's perspective has no bearing on their perception of societal prejudice.

According to Singh and Subedi (2020) sees one advantage in social stigma; employees who are not directly involved in providing care for COVID-19 patients may have a negative attitude toward medical professionals, in this case, physical distance and prevention for spreading the symptoms may be highlighted.

8. What action plan can be developed for the encountered social discrimination among the nurses?

Conclusions

1. The profile of the nurse-respondents is the following;
 - 1.1. This presents that majority of the respondents in a tertiary hospital is 31-40, which means most of the nurses belong to the adult category.
 - 1.2. The gender of nurses, which is primarily composed of females and who, although having superior nursing skills, are frequently subjected to a variety of societal discriminations.
 - 1.3. It is apparent that there are more nurses working and being allocated to the emergency department as a result of the increased number of patients being brought in to that area, particularly during the pandemic.

- 1.4. most of the respondents were in the beginning phase of work.
 2. The assessment on social discrimination encountered by the nurse-respondents;
 - 2.1. The nurses from a tertiary hospital during pandemic somewhat experienced a felt stigma. It concludes that nurses are somewhat being discriminated in a form of self-stigmatization such as shame, remorse, or despair.
 - 2.2. It was discovered that nurses working at a tertiary hospital during a pandemic experienced direct stigma to a large extent. Clearly, during the peak of the pandemic, nurses working in tertiary hospitals were subjected to less-than-favorable actions of other people or situations.
 - 2.3. It was revealed that the nurse-respondents had been exposed to indirect stigma to a great extent; this has a significant impact on the respondents as a direct result of the consequences or results of acts that they have encountered throughout the pandemic. Because of this, certain acts, opportunities, and benefits were taken.
 3. There is a significant relationship between the assessments on social discrimination and the positions of the nurse-respondents.
 4. There is no significant relationship between the assessments on social discrimination and the age, gender, and years of service of the nurse-respondents.
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Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions from this study, the following recommendations were given:

1. The human resource department may balance the age and gender proportions of the nurses to create a diverse but effective health service.
2. The nurse supervisors may provide more assistance on the emergency room to deliver effective and efficient service and avoid some forms of discriminations.
3. The department could start seminars focusing on psychosocial support for nurses, with the goal of encouraging the development of ethics and well-social being in the profession. This will help alleviate the discrimination on felt stigma.
4. A workshop or training may be spearheaded by the department highlighting the stress debriefing and coping mechanisms during emergency cases. This could serve as the basis of the nurses on what action should be taken for direct stigma.
5. The hospital should strengthen holding masses for psychospiritual well-being of the nurses.
6. The hospitals might establish their own local hotline or create a contextualized version of the *sumbungan ng bayan* for nurses so that they can report issues related to indirect stigma. These issues include a lack of opportunities being offered, benefits being hoarded, and activities being prohibited.
7. In addition to the mandated earnings, the government may consider providing additional incentives and privileges to nurses. These may include retreats, funds, gift packages, and other equipment that will motivate and encourage them even during emergency cases.

For future researchers, the following are recommended by this study:

8. Apply another theory to evaluate additional sorts of social discrimination;

9. Include other assessors aside from self-assessment for a wider scope of results and data.
 10. Determine the significant relationship in each type of stigma.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting the study titled “Social Discrimination Among Nurses in a Tertiary Hospital During the COVID-19 Pandemic: An Assessment,” adherence to ethical standards was paramount. Prior to data collection, all participants were provided with a thorough explanation of the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits, ensuring that they were fully informed. Written informed consent was obtained from each participant, affirming their voluntary agreement to participate and their understanding of their right to withdraw at any time without any repercussions. Confidentiality was rigorously maintained throughout the research process; all data collected was securely stored and anonymized to protect participants' identities. The study was conducted with respect to the highest ethical standards to ensure the welfare and rights of all participants were safeguarded.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express her heartfelt appreciation to all those who supported, assisted, and provided invaluable guidance throughout the completion of this study.

First and foremost, a profound thanks to her loving and supportive husband, Capt. Allan C. Alcantara. His unwavering moral support and constant encouragement have been the bedrock of her motivation, enabling her to persevere and successfully finish this research. His belief in her abilities and the countless sacrifices he made during this journey have been deeply cherished.

Additionally, heartfelt gratitude is extended to the managers and staff nurses of Gentry Medical Center and Hospital in General Trias, Cavite. Their invaluable and selfless support has been instrumental in her research. They provided her with essential information, resources, and guidance, which enriched her study and ensured its relevance and accuracy. Their willingness to share their expertise and insights exemplifies a true commitment to collaboration and professional development.

To her family, she offers sincere thanks for their unwavering support and encouragement. Their love and understanding have been a source of strength, and their belief in her potential has fueled her determination to achieve her goals.

Finally, above all, she gives thanks to God, who has provided her with the strength, wisdom, and perseverance needed to overcome challenges and achieve success. It is

through faith and divine guidance that she has found the courage to pursue her research aspirations.

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